

Relation between the Intensity and the Velocity of the Reaction between Potassium Oxalate and Bromine in Visible and Infra-red Radiations.

BY A. K. BHATTACHARYA AND N. R. DEAR.

In a recent communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 473) we have shown that the relation between the incident radiation and the velocity of reaction between bromine and Rochelle salt, sodium formate and iodine, quinine sulphate and chromic acid can vary approximately from $\frac{1}{2}$ to 2. In the case of the reaction between potassium oxalate and iodine, the relation between intensity and velocity varies from $\frac{1}{2}$ to 1. We have carried on similar experiments with potassium oxalate and bromine using different amounts of potassium bromide which is a marked retarder in white light and in radiation of wave-length 7304 Å. The experimental arrangement is the same as described in previous papers. The following results have been obtained at 20°.

N/10-Potassium oxalate and N/100-bromine (10 gm. KBr in 100 c. c. of N/100-bromine), 10 c. c. each.

Diameter of the aperture.	k_1 Unimolecular.	k_1 After deducting the dark reaction: k_1 (dark) = 0.00205.
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A. Source :—Sunlight.

2 cm.	0.0684	0.06635 (I)
0.8	0.0463	0.04125 (II)
0.4	0.0418	0.03975 (III)

B. Source :—1000 watt lamp.

2 cm.	0.0384	0.03635 (I)
0.8	0.0210	0.01895 (II)
0.4	0.0146	0.01265 (III)

N/10-Potassium oxalate and N/100-bromine (2 gm. KBr in 100 c. c. of N/100-bromine).

Diameter of the aperture.	k_1 Unimolecular.	k_1 After deducting the dark reaction : $k_1(\text{dark}) = 0.00456$.
C. Source :—1000 watt lamp.		
2 cm.	0.0770	0.0724 (I)
0.8	0.0400	0.0354 (II)
0.4	0.0254	0.0208 (III)
D. Region :— $\lambda = 7304\text{Å}$.		
2 cm.	0.0203	0.0157 (I)
0.8	0.00976	0.0052 (II)
0.4	0.00693	0.00237 (III)

N/10-Potassium oxalate and N/100-bromine (1 gm. KBr in 100 c.c. of N/100-bromine).

E. Region :— $\lambda = 7304\text{Å}$.		$k_1(\text{dark}) = 0.0194$.
2 cm.	0.0609	0.0415 (I)
0.8	0.0300	0.0106 (II)
0.4	0.0229	0.0035 (III)

N/10-Potassium oxalate and N/100-bromine (0.75 gm. KBr in 100 c.c. of N/100-bromine).

F. Region :— $\lambda = 7304\text{Å}$.		$k_1(\text{dark}) = 0.0365$.
2 cm.	0.0814	0.0449 (I)
0.8	0.0460	0.0095 (II)
0.4	0.0394	0.0029 (III)

Ratio of velocities. If proportional directly to the change in intensity. If proportional to the square-root of the change in intensity.

A. Source :—Sunlight.

$$\frac{\text{I}}{\text{II}} = \frac{0.06635}{0.04425} = 1.5 \qquad \frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25 \qquad \sqrt{6.25} = 2.5$$

$$\frac{\text{II}}{\text{III}} = \frac{0.04425}{0.03975} = 1.11 \qquad \frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4 \qquad \sqrt{4} = 2$$

$$\frac{\text{I}}{\text{III}} = \frac{0.06635}{0.03975} = 1.67 \qquad \frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25 \qquad \sqrt{25} = 5$$

Ratio of velocities. If proportional directly to the change in intensity. If proportional to the square-root of the change in intensity.

B. Source :—1000 watt lamp.

$$\frac{I}{II} = \frac{0.03635}{0.01895} = 1.92 \qquad \frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25 \qquad \sqrt{6.25} = 2.5$$

$$\frac{II}{III} = \frac{0.01895}{0.01255} = 1.51 \qquad \frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4 \qquad \sqrt{4} = 2$$

$$\frac{I}{III} = \frac{0.03635}{0.01255} = 2.9 \qquad \frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25 \qquad \sqrt{25} = 5$$

C. Source :—1000 watt lamp.

$$\frac{I}{II} = \frac{0.0724}{0.0354} = 2.05 \qquad \frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25 \qquad \sqrt{6.25} = 2.5$$

$$\frac{II}{III} = \frac{0.0354}{0.0208} = 1.7 \qquad \frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4 \qquad \sqrt{4} = 2$$

$$\frac{I}{III} = \frac{0.0724}{0.0208} = 3.5 \qquad \frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25 \qquad \sqrt{25} = 5$$

D. Source :— $\lambda = 7304\text{\AA}$ (1000 watt lamp).

$$\frac{I}{II} = \frac{0.0157}{0.0052} = 3 \qquad \frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25 \qquad \sqrt{6.25} = 2.5$$

$$\frac{II}{III} = \frac{0.0052}{0.00237} = 2.2 \qquad \frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4 \qquad \sqrt{4} = 2$$

$$\frac{I}{III} = \frac{0.0157}{0.00237} = 6.6 \qquad \frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25 \qquad \sqrt{25} = 5$$

E. Source :— $\lambda = 7304\text{\AA}$ (1000 watt lamp).

$$\frac{I}{II} = \frac{0.0415}{0.0106} = 3.91 \qquad \frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25 \qquad \sqrt{6.25} = 2.5$$

$$\frac{II}{III} = \frac{0.0106}{0.0035} = 3 \qquad \frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4 \qquad \sqrt{4} = 2$$

$$\frac{I}{III} = \frac{0.0415}{0.0035} = 11.85 \qquad \frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25 \qquad \sqrt{25} = 5$$

F. Source :— $\lambda = 7304\text{\AA}$ (1000 watt lamp).

$$\frac{I}{II} = \frac{0.0449}{0.0095} = 4.73 \qquad \frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25 \qquad \sqrt{6.25} = 2.5$$

$$\frac{II}{III} = \frac{0.0095}{0.0029} = 3.24 \qquad \frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4 \qquad \sqrt{4} = 2$$

$$\frac{I}{III} = \frac{0.0449}{0.0029} = 15.5 \qquad \frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25 \qquad \sqrt{25} = 5$$

The experimental results show that the relation between intensity and the velocity of the reaction varies from $1/4$ to 1 depending on the ratio of the light reaction and the thermal reaction. These results are in entire agreement with our conclusion that the relation between the intensity and velocity of a reaction is controlled by the ratio of light and dark reaction. In order to make sure that the absorption of radiation is proportional to the intensity of the incident radiation, we have determined the absorption of the incident radiation by a radiomicrometer and the results are as follows :

Diameter of the aperture.	Distilled water (deflection).	$N/10\text{-K}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$ and $N/100\text{-Br}_2$ in 2 gms. KBr (deflection).	Difference in deflection.	
2 cm.	37.1 cm.	34.1 cm.	3 cm.	
0.8	8.1	5.65	0.45	
0.4	1.55	1.45	0.1	
Diameter of the aperture	...	2.0	0.8	0.4 cm.
Area	...	3.14	0.5024	0.1256 sq cm.

Ratio of intensity.

$$\frac{\text{I}}{\text{II}} = \frac{3.14}{0.5024} = 6.25$$

$$\frac{\text{II}}{\text{III}} = \frac{0.5024}{0.1256} = 4.$$

$$\frac{\text{I}}{\text{III}} = \frac{3.14}{0.1256} = 25$$

Ratio of absorption.

$$\frac{3}{0.45} = 6.66$$

$$\frac{0.45}{0.10} = 4.5$$

$$\frac{3}{0.1} = 30$$

Hence the amount of absorption of radiation of $7304\text{\AA}$ by a mixture of potassium oxalate and bromine is directly proportional to the intensity of the incident radiation.

The foregoing results conclusively prove that the relation between velocity of the reaction between potassium oxalate and bromine in radiation of $7304\text{\AA}$ and both the intensity of the incident radiation and the amount of absorption can vary from $1/4$ to 1 depending on ratio of the velocity of the dark and light reactions.

We are of the opinion that the velocity of this reaction as well as those of several other reactions may be proportional to $I^{1/2}$ in presence of strong light from a mercury lamp.

It will be interesting to note that the velocity of the reaction between hydrogen and bromine has been found to be proportional to the square-root of both the absorbed energy (Bodenstein and

Lütkemeyer, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, **114**, 208) and incident radiation (Briers and Chapman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **133**, 1807). The same reaction appears to be directly proportional to the intensity (Briers and Chapman) of the incident radiation when the intensity is low.

Our results show that the reaction between potassium oxalate and bromine is markedly accelerated in the region $7304\text{\AA}$ which cannot atomise the bromine molecules ($6280\text{\AA}$ is necessary to atomise bromine). Moreover, the relation between the velocity of a reaction and intensity is not always $\frac{1}{2}$; hence the conception of Berthoud (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1924, **7**, 307) that bromine molecules are atomised in light is not upheld by our experiments.

Summary.

(1) Experimental results show that the relation between the velocity of the reaction between potassium oxalate and bromine and the intensity of the incident radiation or the amount of energy absorbed can be varied approximately from $1/4$ to unity, depending on the ratio of the thermal and photochemical velocities of the same reaction

(2) By the absorption of radiation, chlorine, bromine, and iodine are not atomised in most cases but the molecules are activated by the absorption of incident energy and chemically react.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY OF ALLAHABAD.

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